

Digital Eyes on Honey

Ensuring Authenticity in the Food Chain

White Paper

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Abstract

Ensuring honey authenticity has become a priority in the global food industry, as adulteration with cheaper sugars and mislabeling of botanical origin undermines consumer confidence and damage producer credibility. Portable near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy and hyperspectral imaging (HSI) technologies provide rapid, non-destructive, and reliable tools for on-site detection of food adulteration. This study, part of the European project Watson, assessed the performance of several portable NIR and HSI devices across different measurement modes and configurations as part of a pilot in honey. These findings highlight the potential of portable spectroscopic technologies to enhance the capabilities of regulatory agencies, quality control laboratories, and producers in verifying honey purity and authenticity.

Introduction

Honey is one of the most valued natural sweeteners, a complex matrix of sugars, enzymes, amino acids, and bioactive compounds known for their nutritional and therapeutic properties. Its composition reflects both botanical and geographical origins, making honey a product intrinsically linked to biodiversity and regional identity. However, its high market value has also made it a prime target for adulteration. Common practices include dilution with cheap syrups and misrepresentation of floral source or geographical origin.

Traditional laboratory-based authentication methods include isotopic, physicochemical, and pollen analyses, which offer high accuracy but are time-consuming, costly, and rely on specialized expertise. As a result, there is a growing demand for faster, more accessible, and non-destructive analytical tools capable of real-time operation.

In this context, near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy and hyperspectral imaging (HSI) are emerging as transformative technologies. Both methods are based on the interaction between light and matter, where specific wavelengths of light are absorbed or reflected depending on the molecular structure and composition of the material.

NIR spectroscopy measures how honey absorbs light in the near-infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum. It can operate in reflectance, transmittance, or transfectance modes, extracting chemical and physical information based on molecular vibrations

The resulting spectra act as a chemical “fingerprint,” revealing information about key constituents. On the other hand, HSI extends this capacity capturing both spatial and spectral data. This produces detailed chemical maps that visualize variations in composition or impurities across the sample surface.

By exploiting light-matter interactions with technologies such as NIR and HSI, we can perform a rapid characterization of honey, supporting *in-situ* verification that enhances traceability, transparency, and consumer trust across the honey value chain. The accuracy of these technologies relies on the spectral differences between authentic honey and adulterated ones. With new, honey-like syrups becoming more common, updating calibration models by incorporating examples of these novel adulterants strengthens their robustness and extends their detection capabilities.

The Technological Approach

NIR spectroscopy covers the 700-2500 nm spectral range, providing molecular information through overtones and combinations of C–H, O–H, and N–H vibrations. HSI extends this capability by capturing both spatial and spectral data in the 400-2500 nm range, creating a “spectral fingerprint” for each pixel of an image.

Both methods are non-destructive, fast, and capable of simultaneous analysis of multiple components. Recent advances in miniaturization have led to handheld and portable devices, enabling in-field authenticity verification. When coupled with advanced chemometric models and machine learning, these technologies enable accurate classification of honey purity and botanical origin.

Materials and Methods

A total of 148 honey samples were analyzed, including 78 pure and 70 intentionally adulterated using different concentrations (5-40%) of three syrups: two rice-based and one corn-based. Measurements were performed using several portable NIR devices (InnoSpectra NIR-S-G1, NIR-S-T2, Senseen NIR) and a benchtop ASD LabSpec 4, alongside a portable Specim IQ hyperspectral camera for HSI imaging (400-1000 nm). Samples were analyzed in reflectance, transmittance, and transreflectance modes in the case of NIR, and reflectance and transmittance in the case of HSI, both under controlled thickness (0.4-10 mm) and temperature (<40 °C) to prevent crystallization. In the case of HSI, various lighting configurations were tested to ensure uniform illumination, using a white reference surface, using controlled halogen lighting at a 45° angle and with a metallic dome to eliminate direct illumination shadows.

Data processing involved several stages, where a pre-treatment is performed first to enhance signal quality and remove noise, followed by the model development step, using chemometric and machine-learning techniques on 80% of the samples collected, ensuring sample representativeness, consistency and diversity. The developed model is validated subsequently, using the remaining 20% of spectra data. As part of this work, a graphical interface was developed for real-time results in classification and visualization.

Results

Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy

Among the measurement modes tested, transmittance and transreflectance mode provided the most reliable and reproducible spectra for honey analysis. In contrast, reflectance mode proved largely ineffective due to strong interference from water absorption.

To compare these configurations, three portable NIR devices were evaluated in diffuse reflectance mode, and two (one portable and one tabletop) were used for transmittance measurements. This multi-instrument approach enabled a comprehensive assessment of different acquisition techniques and the optimization of measurement conditions for honey authentication.

Systematic testing determined that sample thicknesses of 10 mm and 2 mm for transmittance mode and 1.5 mm and 0.5 mm for transreflectance mode produced the most accurate and consistent spectra. Combining multiple acquisition modes and devices strengthened the robustness of the dataset, leading to a more comprehensive spectral characterization of honey authenticity.

Distinct spectral features differentiating pure and adulterated honeys were identified in the 1250-1350 nm, 1450 nm, and 1650 nm regions, corresponding to overtone bands of C-H and O-H groups.

Hyperspectral imaging (HSI)

In the case of HSI, controlled lighting conditions were essential to obtain consistent and reproducible spectral data. The reflectance mode configuration proved optimal, with the camera positioned directly above the sample and the illumination positioned at a 45° angle. Using a white reference background beneath the sample minimized shadow effects, an issue observed during transmittance measurements using a dome and halogen light ring. This optimized setup enhanced spectral consistency, reduced unwanted artifacts, and improved discrimination between pure and adulterated honey samples. Spectral ranges applied were 930 to 1670 nm for all NIR devices and 430 to 970 nm for the Specim IQ camera, excluding boundary regions with high noise levels to ensure data reliability.

Data Processing and Classification Performance

Comprehensive data pre-treatment was critical to improve spectral quality before analysis, including noise reduction, outlier detection, and normalization. After pre-processing, classification models were developed and tested. Preliminary results using Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) showed over 93% accuracy in identifying adulterated samples. Dataset were divided into training and test sets, and 10-fold cross-validation was applied to ensure robust evaluation of model performance.

To enhance usability, a Python-based graphical interface was developed to visualize and interpret results in real time. The interface provides immediate predictions of honey purity and botanical origin, making the tool accessible to non-experts.

Criteria	Physico-Chemical	Isotopic analysis	Pollen analysis	Watson NIR/HSI
Accuracy	Very high	Very high	High	Moderate to high
Time	Hours to days	Hours to days	Hours to days	On real time (minutes)
Cost per analysis	High	High	Medium	Low
Sample preparation	Complex (extraction and chemical treatments)	Complex (extraction and chemical treatments)	Low	Minimal (pre-heating at 30°C)
Portability	Requires fixed lab setup	Requires fixed lab setup	Requires fixed lab setup	Handheld devices
Operator skills requirement	Needs trained personnel	Needs trained personnel	Needs trained personnel	Minimal training required

Discussion

The integration NIR spectroscopy and HSI, supported by machine learning algorithms, offers a transformative pathway for non-destructive honey authentication. Compared with traditional laboratory analyses, this combined approach enables rapid, cost-effective, and field-deployable detection of adulteration. By drastically reducing analysis time and minimizing operator dependency, these technologies make advanced authentication more accessible across the honey value chain.

Despite its potential, real-world implementation faces challenges. Sample presentation is a critical factor, as inconsistencies in thickness, crystallization, or bubble formation can compromise spectral reliability and reproducibility. Additionally, while portable NIR devices are relatively affordable and user-friendly, some HSI systems remain costly and complex, requiring trained personnel for operation and data interpretation, factors that may limit the adoption among small producers or under-resource laboratories. Instrument calibration and maintenance present further operational barriers, especially for devices deployed in the field where environmental variability can affect stability. Moreover, the regulatory acceptance of these techniques as official authentication methods remains limited. To gain formal recognition, further validation and standardization across diverse sample sets, production contexts, and regions will be necessary.

Nevertheless, portable NIR and HSI technologies demonstrate great prospective as complementary tools to existing analytical methods, particularly for rapid screening and field-level quality control.

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